

In Search of Dark Infrared Clouds: An Algorithm To Project Structural Models of the Milky Way Spirals Onto The Observable Sky

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we exploit the Sun's position at 25pc above the natural plane of the Milky Way Galaxy to detect spiral features of the Milky Way using pre-existing models. This was done in order to test the hypothesis that dark-infrared clouds sketch the center of the spiral arms on to the sky. In order to test this hypothesis, we took models of the Milky Way spiral arms (Vallee 2013, Dame et. al 2008) and converted the continuous spiral structures in these models to a collection of discrete points. Thereafter, we converted the galactocentric coordinates (l , b , distance) of these points to heliocentric coordinates (RA/Dec/Distance), which were then plotted onto the two dimensional projection of the sky (as viewed from the Earth) using World Wide Telescope. Different arms projected different and distinct points onto the sky. We then sought out fine dark-infrared cloud bands near the areas that we predict the spiral arms would be located on the sky using these models. Ultimately, at least one likely candidate for cloud like cores of spiral arms was found using this technique.

BACKGROUND:

The Nessie Nebula is a filamentary infrared dark cloud (IRDC) that is centered near (l , b) = (338.4°, -0.4°) in the Milky Way. The Nessie Nebula consists of numerous dense, compact molecular 'cores', which are spaced roughly 4.5 pc apart along the filament (Jackson et al.). Molecular emission from the Nebula indicates that the components have the same radial velocity 38 (+/- 3.4 km/s) - which indicates that the

filament is not a chance alignment on the sky but actually continuous in nature.

In addition to this, it might be the case that IRDCs are indeed able to trace out the core/ ‘spine’ of the spiral arms of the galaxy. Goodman et. al estimate that a careful analysis of the Spitzer images for Nessie indicate that if it is situated 3.1 kpc away from the sun in the Scutum Centaurus Arm as predicted by Jackson et. al, it is at least 80pc long and could be as much as 430 pc (9 degrees on the sky!). In addition to this, Goodman et. al believe that the axial ratio of Nessie is at least 150 and could be as much as 800 if the Nebula is 430 pc long. In short, Nessie is a thin, long and dark feature in the Milky Way - properties which make it (and other IRDCs like this) especially important in the task of modeling the Milky Way, which will be the focal point of this paper.

Fig 1 (Goodman et al.) -- A Spitzer image with altered contrast to emphasise Nessie. The classical Nessie is shown in the middle is ~ 80 pc long, the Nessie Extended is ~160 pc long and the Nessie Optimistic is ~430 pc long. These have axial ratios of 150, 300, 800 respectively. Goodman et. al argue that Nessie is at least as long as Nessie Extended and could be longer - as in the case with Nessie Optimistic. The yellow horizontal lines show $b = 0$ and $b = -0.5$. The small

white numbers show galactic longitude in degrees. For clarity, it is recommended that the electronic version, complete with zoom and pan features, of this image is viewed:

https://www.authorea.com/users/23/articles/249/master/file/figures/1nessie_findingchart/1nessie_findingchart_hires.jpg

Assuming that objects such as the Nessie Nebula trace out the spine of the arms of the Milky Way and if their extent is as long as that suggested by Goodman et al, then these objects could trace out the Milky Way spiral arms. With regards to this, then, it appears that finding a collection of Nessie-Like objects in the Milky Way can help flesh out the exact locations of the Milky Way spiral arms. However, a challenge to doing so is that the sun is located extremely close to the galactic plane, as do the spirals, which makes it difficult to discern the different spirals. Moreover, the three-dimensional Milky Way is reduced to a two-dimensional plane on the observable sky, making it difficult to distinguish between foreground and background objects through observation alone. This is especially true because it is not necessary that IRDC in the foreground look more distinct than those in the background, as there might not be enough background light to illuminate the foreground clouds (Goodman et al) - making our observations biased to detecting the more well illuminated objects. Thus, it is important to be able to predict where objects such as Nessie can be found and to selectively search for them. Preliminary work on doing this was done by Goodman et al. (Figure 2), who found that Nessie's location can be predicted as that in the center of the Scutum Centaurus arm, as

predicted by the Dame et. al model.

Fig 2 (Goodman et. al) -- CO velocity data (Dame et al. 2001) is used to predict the location of the Scutum Centaurus Arm on the sky. Nessie Classic is then overlaid, which makes it appear to be perfect fit to where the 'center' of the spiral arm would be. The color indicates the intensity of CO emission in the given velocity range.

by overlaying the center of the Scutum Centaurus arm, as predicted by Dame et al., and then overlaying the position of Nessie Classic onto this model. As Fig 2 indicates, the position of Nessie Classic could be predicted by the Scutum Centaurus arm.

In this paper, I will extend this idea of using a model for the spiral arms to predict where IRDCs such as Nessie could be found - this could then be used to further study these IRDCs to confirm/reject whether they are truly placed in the arms. However, for this to be useful, it is important to ensure that spiral features that are

being sought (ie the centers of the arm) can be discerned in the two-dimensional plane of the sky. This presents a challenge due to the Sun's location in the galactic plane as defined by the IAU. An opportunity, however, arises because the galactic plane as defined by the IAU is not the true galactic plane. Indeed, the Sun is located 25 pc above the true galactic plane (in the IAU $b = 0$ plane), thus allowing astronomers to look 'down' onto the true galactic plane to see features. However, because the sun is still extremely close to the true galactic plane, only very distinct and thin objects can be discerned clearly - objects such as Nessie!

Fig 3 -- A rough schematic (**not to scale**) of the Milky Way Plane, as defined by the IAU along with the “assumed plane” used in this paper and the true galactic plane.

In this paper, we will use a model of the Milky Way Spirals (Vallee 2013) of the Milky Way to predict the location of spiral arms. We will then trace out these arms in galactocentric coordinates and then project these onto the two-dimensional plane of the sky using RA/Dec. We will do this using an ‘imaginary’ galactic plane

which is parallel to the galactic plane as defined by the IAU and 25 pc below it.

Doing so allows the angle that the true galactic plane makes with the IAU plane to be ignored. Using this imaginary galactic plane is still close enough to the original to provide a good estimate for where the features would be in the true galactic plane, especially for the parts of the arms that are closer to the sun! Indeed, these parts should be easier to see in the two-dimensional projection as the objects further away would be difficult to see due to the numerous foreground objects that could shadow them.

This RA/Dec data for each arm, along with the measurement of the distance of each point in the arm from the center of the imaginary galaxy will then be overlaid with GLIMPSE data and an attempt will be made to find Nessie-like objects.

METHODS:

In order to project models of the Milky Way onto the two dimensional plane of the sky, a robust pipeline needed to be made. Making a flexible pipeline for doing this not only allows future users to compare multiple models together, but also lets the models to be altered flexibly and then projected.

For the purpose of this project, this pipeline was constructed to handle models of the Milky Way as logarithmic spirals. The initial steps in this procedure was to parametrize any given logarithmic spiral and then generate points that satisfy this parametrization for a given range. In general, logarithmic spirals can be represented in the following way with the x and y coordinates being galactocentric:

$$x(t) = r(t) \cos(t) \quad \text{--- (1)}$$

$$y(t) = r(t) \sin(t) \quad \text{--- (2)}$$

where $r(t) = a e^{bt}$ --- (3)

Moreover,

$$\arctan(1/b) = \varphi \quad \text{--- (4)}$$

In addition to this, the angle φ is the complement of the pitch angle δ . In other words

$$90 - \varphi = \delta \text{ (all angles in degrees)} \quad \text{--- (5)}$$

Combining equation (4) and (5), we obtain:

$$b = 1/[\tan(90 - \delta) \text{ in degrees}] \quad \text{--- (6)}$$

From analyzing the limit, we also note that a is the x-intercept of the logarithmic spiral when the variable parameter t is set to zero.

$$x(0) = a \quad \text{--- (7)}$$

Fig 4 (Vallee) -- A diagram that represents a four-arm galactocentric model of the Milky Way. Notice that the x-intercept and y-intercepts can easily be determined for the four arms. In addition to this, the values of the t parameter can also be selected to create this particular set. Note that the value of the z axis is zero.

From inspecting the Vallee 2013 model in Figure 4, we can deduce the a parameter for the four logarithmic spirals, as follows. Note, however, that the scutum/blue data is not from the Vallee 2013 model but through the more accurate Dame et al. 2008 model :

$$\begin{aligned}
 a_{normal/red} &= -4750 \text{ pc (pitch angle} = 12.8 \text{ degrees)} \\
 a_{scutum/blue} &= -5450 \text{ pc (pitch angle} = 14.2 \text{ degrees)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$a_{sagittarius/green} = -9750 \text{ pc (pitch angle} = 12.8 \text{ degrees)}$$

$$a_{perseus/yellow} = -3250 \text{ pc (pitch angle} = 12.8 \text{ degrees)}$$

From the diagram, we can also measure that range of the parameter t (in degrees) for each of the arms.

$$-30 \leq t_{normal/red} \leq 330$$

$$-120 \leq t_{scutum/blue} \leq 240$$

$$-300 \leq t_{sagittarius/green} \leq 60$$

$$-210 \leq t_{perseus/yellow} \leq 150$$

From this information, software that can plot mathematical functions can be used to plot these logarithmic spirals to confirm that the parametrization is correct. For this purpose, I used “Wolfram Mathematica: For Students” to create a separate graphic for each arm.

```
(* Parametrization of the Scutum Centaurus Arm (Blue) *)
(*Note that the x range has been changed to degrees because this is required
in Mathematica
*)
```

```
In[53]:= pb = ParametricPlot[{-5450 * (E^(x/Tan[(90 - 14.2) Degree])) * Cos[x],
-5450 * (E^(x/Tan[(90 - 14.2) Degree])) * Sin[x]},
{x, -Pi - 0.52359, 2 * Pi - Pi - 0.52359}, PlotRange -> Automatic]
```


Fig 5.1 -- The Scutum Centaurus Arm (Blue in Fig 4) model as presented by Dame et al 2008, as input into Mathematica. Note that z (coordinate) = 0 . Note that the units are in parsecs

Fig 5.2 -- The Perseus Arm (Yellow in Fig 4) model as presented by Vallee, as input into Mathematica. Note that z (axis) = 0 and that the units are in parsec

```

(*) Parametrization of the Norma Arm (Red) *)
(*Note that the x range has been changed to degrees because this is required
in Mathematica
*)

In[47]:= pr = ParametricPlot[{-4750 * (E ^ (x/Tan[(90 - 12.8) Degree])) * Cos [x],
-4750 * (E ^ (x/Tan[(90 - 12.8) Degree])) * Sin[x]},
{x, -Pi + 1.04719, 2 * Pi - Pi + 1.04719}, PlotRange -> Automatic]

```


Fig 5.3 -- The Norma Arm (Red in Fig 4) model as presented by Vallee, as input into Mathematica. Note that z (*axis*) = 0. Note that the units are in parsecs

```

(*)          Parametrization of the Sagittarius Arm (Green) *)
(*Note that the x range has been changed to degrees because this is required
in Mathematica
*)

In[49]:= pg = ParametricPlot[{-9750 * (E ^ (x / Tan[(90 - 12.8) Degree])) * Cos[x],
-9750 * (E ^ (x / Tan[(90 - 12.8) Degree])) * Sin[x]}, {x, -2 * Pi + 1.0471, 1.0471},
PlotRange -> Automatic]

```


Fig 5.4 -- The Sagittarius Arm (Green in Fig 4) model as presented by Vallee, as input into Mathematica. Note that z (axis) = 0. Note that the axis is in parsecs.

Thereafter, every arm was plotted on a single plane to generate the model in Fig 5. Notice how the Fig 5 resembles Fig 4 very closely.

Fig 6 -- A Mathematica plot that reproduce the model in Valee and Dame models (Figures 5.1 - 5.4 combined). Note that, unlike Fig 4, the axis is in units of parsecs. Moreover, the value of the z-plane is zero.

In order to project these models onto the sky, specific points that fit the functional forms of these arms had to be generated. This was due to the fact that the most recent version of World Wide Telescope - the visualization software that was going to be used for projecting the spiral model onto the sky - can only plot discrete points. However, in order to be able to discern the spirals on the projected sky, it was important to have some continuity. Therefore, approximately 8000 points were generated for each arm. This was done using Mathematica's Table function that allows a function to be evaluated through constant increments of the original value.

The code that was written to achieve this is pasted in Fig 6.

```
In[32]= Table[{ -4750 * (E ^ (x / Tan[(90 - 12.8) Degree ])) * Cos [x],  
-4750 * (E ^ (x / Tan[(90 - 12.8) Degree ])) * Sin[x], 0},  
{x, -Pi + 1.04719, 2 * Pi - Pi + 1.04719, 2 * Pi / 8000}]  
m = N[%]  
Export["Norma.csv", m]
```

A very large output was generated. Here is a sample of it:

```
Out[32]= {{1475.76, 2556.05, 0}, {1474.02, 2557.66, 0}, {1472.27, 2559.28, 0}, {1470.52, 2560.89, 0},  
<<7994>>, {6165.92, 10640.9, 0}, {6158.66, 10647.6, 0}, {6151.39, 10654.3, 0}}
```

Show Less Show More Show Full Output Set Size Limit...

A very large output was generated. Here is a sample of it:

```
Out[33]= {{1475.76, 2556.05, 0.}, {1474.02, 2557.66, 0.},  
{1472.27, 2559.28, 0.}, {1470.52, 2560.89, 0.}, <<7994>>,  
{6165.92, 10640.9, 0.}, {6158.66, 10647.6, 0.}, {6151.39, 10654.3, 0.}}
```

Show Less Show More Show Full Output Set Size Limit...

Out[34]= Norma.csv

```
In[29]= Table[{ -3250 * (E ^ (x / Tan[(90 - 12.8) Degree ])) * Cos [x],  
-3250 * (E ^ (x / Tan[(90 - 12.8) Degree ])) * Sin[x], 0},  
{x, -Pi / 2 + 1.04719, 2 * Pi - Pi / 2 + 1.04719, 2 * Pi / 8000}]  
m = N[%]  
Export["Perseus.csv", m]
```

A very large output was generated. Here is a sample of it:

```
Out[29]= {{-2498.9, 1442.76, 0}, {-2500.47, 1441.06, 0},  
{-2502.05, 1439.35, 0}, {-2503.63, 1437.64, 0}, <<7994>>,  
{-10402.9, 6028.05, 0}, {-10409.5, 6020.95, 0}, {-10416.1, 6013.85, 0}}
```

Show Less Show More Show Full Output Set Size Limit...

A very large output was generated. Here is a sample of it:

```
Out[30]= {{-2498.9, 1442.76, 0.}, {-2500.47, 1441.06, 0.},  
{-2502.05, 1439.35, 0.}, {-2503.63, 1437.64, 0.}, <<7994>>,  
{-10402.9, 6028.05, 0.}, {-10409.5, 6020.95, 0.}, {-10416.1, 6013.85, 0.}}
```

Show Less Show More Show Full Output Set Size Limit...

Out[31]= Perseus.csv

```

In[67]:= Table[{ -5450 * (E ^ (x / Tan [ (90 - 14.2) Degree ])) * Cos [x],
               -5450 * (E ^ (x / Tan [ (90 - 14.2) Degree ])) * Sin [x], 0},
               {x, -Pi - 0.52359, 2 * Pi - Pi - 0.52359, 2 * Pi / 8000}]
m = N[%]
Export ["Scutum.csv", m]

```

A very large output was generated. Here is a sample of it:

```

Out[67]= {{1867.02, -1077.91, 0}, {1868.24, -1076.65, 0},
          {1869.46, -1075.4, 0}, {1870.67, -1074.14, 0}, <<7994>>,
          {9142.47, -5297.46, 0}, {9148.44, -5291.33, 0}, {9154.41, -5285.2, 0}}

```

Show Less Show More Show Full Output Set Size Limit...

A very large output was generated. Here is a sample of it:

```

Out[68]= {{1867.02, -1077.91, 0.}, {1868.24, -1076.65, 0.},
          {1869.46, -1075.4, 0.}, {1870.67, -1074.14, 0.}, <<7994>>,
          {9142.47, -5297.46, 0.}, {9148.44, -5291.33, 0.}, {9154.41, -5285.2, 0.}}

```

Show Less Show More Show Full Output Set Size Limit...

Out[69]= Scutum.csv

```

Table[{ -9750 * (E ^ (x / Tan [ (90 - 12.8) Degree ])) * Cos [x],
        -9750 * (E ^ (x / Tan [ (90 - 12.8) Degree ])) * Sin [x], 0},
        {x, -2 * Pi + 1.0471, 1.0471, 2 * Pi / 8000}]
m = N[%]
Export ["Sagittarius.csv", m]

```

A very large output was generated. Here is a sample of it:

```

Out[10]= {{-1483.91, -2569.63}, {-1482.15, -2571.25}, {-1480.4, -2572.87},
          <<7995>>, {-6199.96, -10697.4}, {-6192.66, -10704.2}, {-6185.35, -10710.9}}

```

Show Less Show More Show Full Output Set Size Limit...

A very large output was generated. Here is a sample of it:

```

Out[11]= {{-1483.91, -2569.63}, {-1482.15, -2571.25}, {-1480.4, -2572.87},
          <<7995>>, {-6199.96, -10697.4}, {-6192.66, -10704.2}, {-6185.35, -10710.9}}

```

Show Less Show More Show Full Output Set Size Limit...

Out[12]= Sagittarius.csv

Fig 6 -- A collection of Mathematica code that was used to generate ~ 8000 points to fit each of the four spiral arms. The output columns of the .csv files included the galactocentric x and y coordinates (note that z = 0 for the Vallee models).

After obtaining these models, the galactocentric coordinates were put into an IDL conversion program (Goodman et al. - code written by Chris Beaumont and Robert Benjamin is attached in Appendix A) that converted these galactocentric coordinates into heliocentric RA/Dec and also computed the distance from the sun of these points. In this program the Sun's position as (x, y, z) was selected as $(-8500, 0, 25)$ and the position of x, y position each of the arms were given by the columns of the generated .csv files. Note that -8500 refers to the x distance from the assumed plane galactic center at $(0,0,0)$ and 25 is the height above the galactic plane. The z position was selected as 0 for all of these points, as per the tabular conversion given in Figure 6. For reference, the converted data containing the $x, y, z, RA, Dec, Distance$ for all the arms is attached in Appendix B.

RESULTS:

After obtaining the data spreadsheets and plotting them in World Wide Telescope , the visual output was checked against that generated by Goodman et. al to ensure that the algorithm was functioning properly. This was done by projecting the Scutum-Centaurus (Blue) arm, as parametrized by Dame et. al (2008) onto the two dimensional plane of the sky. Given the hypothesis mentioned earlier, it was expected that the Scutum Centaurus arm would intersect the Nessie Nebula. As per the expectation, this was the case, as can be seen in Figure 7a/b!

Figure 7a (top, Goodman et. al) -- The position of the Galactic Plane for the near side of the Scutum Centaurus (approximate 3.1 kpc from the Sun) is shown. Note that this passes through the Nessie Nebula. GLIMPSE in background.

Figure7b (bottom) -- The position of the Scutum Centaurus arm as constructed in World Wide Telescope (GLIMPSE data in the background). Notice the perfect alignment of the arm's 'spine' onto the Nessie Nebula! The dotted line refers to the part of the arm that is closer to the Sun (foreground) and the straight line refers to the background arm. .

After this initial check, the remaining spiral-arm models, as modeled by Vallee 2013, were used to generate projections of the arms onto the two-dimensional plane of the sky. The data that were plotted in World Wide Telescope are provided in Appendix B for reference.

Fig 8 -- The projection of Scutum Centaurus (blue), Norma (Red), Sagittarius (Green) and Perseus (Yellow) arms onto the sky. Note that the dotted segments are the parts of the arms in the foreground. Note also the curvature of the Sagittarius arm can easily be discerned (the smaller part is foreground). The 25pc vantage point allows for nearby arms segments (Scutum Crux, Norma and Perseus) to be discerned more easily than the background components of these.

Upon plotting this data and inspecting it, it became clear that the 25pc vantage point actually allows a significant amount of differentiation between the arms to be detected on the sky. However, as mentioned in the ‘Background’ section, only very thin, long, and dark objects that could potentially define the spine of the spiral arms could be seen clearly. Fuzzier or more diffuse objects would appear to be between different arms and it would thus be difficult to make predictions of which arm they belong to if this were the case. However, as can be seen in Fig 8, objects such as Nessie are distinct and thin enough to be attributed to a single arm (25 pc above the $z = 0$ plane is still quite close to the plane!) and thus it seems reasonable to look for objects such as these in the remaining arms, as was outset in the Background section of this paper.

Upon plotting the spiral arms, the GLIMPSE overlay was visually inspected to find Nessie-like objects. This yielded numerous candidates, the best of which were selected for discussion in this paper and are shown in Figure 9 and Figure 10. Note that it is visually difficult to find thin IRDCs because a lack of background light can make them difficult to find, especially towards the edges of the Milky Way, which appear dimmer in GLIMPSE data. A complete compilation of all the candidates is provided in Appendix C along with a brief discussion of the challenges of a visual inspection.

Fig 10 -- The rightmost segment of the Norma arm (as predicted by Vallee 2013) contains a thin, filamentary IRDC appears to be similar to the Nessie Nebula. Note that the IRDC is situated at the very center of the spiral.

Fig 10 -- The rightmost segment of the Norma arm (as predicted by Vallee 2013) contains a thin, filamentary IRDC appears to be similar to the Nessie Nebula. Note that the IRDC is situated at the very center of the spiral.

CONCLUSION:

The algorithm that was developed during the course of this project to project models of the Milky Way onto the two dimensional plane of the sky yields the same results as the ones proposed by Goodman et. al for the location of the Nessie Nebula at the ‘spine’ of the Scutum-Centaurus Arm. This adds credibility to this pipeline’s correctness. In addition to this, multiple candidates for thin IRDCs were found at the ‘spines’ of other arms, with at least one very similar IRDC in the Norma Arm (as characterized by Vallee 2013).

On the basis of the projection alone, it is difficult to be completely certain of whether these objects are truly in the Perseus and Norma Arms and an analysis of radial

velocities of these clouds is suggested to further test the original hypothesis that such objects would demarcate the spines of spiral arms. Radial velocity analysis was, however, beyond the scope of this paper and was not carried out.

Nevertheless, the algorithm developed successfully yielded candidates for a future study of the location of filamentary IRDCs at the heart of spiral arms.

REMARKS: For future programmers who would like to expand this pipeline, it is encouraged that they account for the tilt of the Milky Way's true plane. This would be useful for very precise measurements but was ignored for this pipeline because the tilt angle is not significant enough to translate the projections visibly.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS:

It is my greatest pleasure to thank the following people for their help, support and guidance in the completion of this paper.

This paper owes its inspiration to the work done previously by Dr. Alyssa Goodman, Dr. Robert Benjamin, Dr. Thomas Dame and others in using the Sun's location to learn more about the Milky Way Structure. I am indebted to the constant guidance and patience of Dr. Alyssa Goodman and Dr. Douglas Finkbeiner, who helped me grow both personally and academically this semester. This project could not have been completed without the generosity of Prof. Benjamin and Christopher Beaumont in teaching me more about IDL and UNIX and sharing their code - which served as a key component in my algorithm. I would also like to thank Dr. Thomas Dame's constant support in finding the best parametrization of the Milky Way spirals, which served as a cornerstone to this paper.

My special appreciation goes to all of my teachers and mentors, especially, Haroon Ali Agha, Zubia Kazmi, Ghazala Mufti, Dr. David Charbonneau, Dr. John Huchra, Dr. Daniel Eisenstein, Dr. Thomas Dame, Meredith Ann MacGregor, Dr. David Morin, Dr. Bradley Whitmore, Dr. Stefi O’Dea, Dr. Chris O’Dea.

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CITATIONS:

1) “The Bones of the Milky Way”

Goodman et. al Draft:

URL: https://www.authorea.com/users/23/articles/249/_show_article

2) “A New Spiral Arm of the Galaxy: The Far 3 kpc Arm”

Dame & Thaddeus (2008)

The Astrophysical Journal, Volume 683, Issue 2, pp. L143-L146.

3) “A Synthesis of Fundamental Parameters of Spiral Arms, Based on Recent Observations in the Milky Way”

Jacques P. Vallee (2013)

International Journal of Astronomy and Astrophysics, 2013, 3, 20-28

4) Spitzer Space Telescope Data (especially GLIMPSE)

5) Software: Wolfram Mathematica, IDL, World Wide Telescope, Microsoft Excel, Google Refine

APPENDIX A

THIS APPENDIX CONTAINS OUTSIDE CODE THAT WAS NOT WRITTEN BY THE AUTHOR. THIS CODE WAS USED TO CONVERT BETWEEN COORDINATE SYSTEMS AND DETERMINE DISTANCES.

XYZ (parsecs) to RA/Dec (Degrees) Conversion Code by Dr. Robert Benjamin & Christopher Beaumont

```
pro mw_coord, f1in, g1in, h1in, itype, f2, g2, h2, RSUN=rsun, XSUN=xsun, YSUN=ysun, ZSUN=zsun, $
    AZ360=AZ360, AZSORT=azsort, ABSMAG=absmag, ROTXY=rotxy, PITCH=pitch, RINNER=rin
; -----
; INPUTS
;   f1,g1,h1=three input coordinates (single values or any size/dimension array)
; OUTPUTS:
;   f2, g2, h2 are three output coordinates (same dimensions as input arrays)
;
; OPTIONS:
; XSUN: X-position of Sun with respect to Galactic center (= —Rsun)
; YSUN: normally zero, but changing this allows you to position the "sun" anywhere
; ZSUN: distance of sun above/below the Galactic plane
; AZ360: galactic longitude/azimuth changed from (-180 to +180) to (0 to 360)
; PITCH: pitch angle assumed for spiral coordinate system
; ROTXY is the *angle* that the x-y coordinates should be rotated
;   ROTXY=0. is standard orientation (sun at X=-Rsun, Y=0), L=90 at top of plot
;   ROTXY=90 is sun at (X=XX, Y=YY), L=XX at top of plot.
;   ROTXY=180 is sun at (X=XX, Y=YY), L=XX at top of plot.
;   ROTXY=270 is sun at (X=XX, Y=YY), L=XX at top of plot.
;   Dependency: Uses rotate_xy.pro from JHU library
; -----
f1=double(f1in) & g1=double(g1in) & h1=double(h1in)
; -----
; Default parameters
; -----

IF keyword_set(XSUN) AND keyword_set(RSUN) THEN stop, 'Only set Xsun or Rsun'
IF keyword_set(RSUN) THEN XS=rsun ELSE XS=!XSUN
IF keyword_set(XSUN) THEN XS=xsun ELSE XS=!XSUN
XS=float(XS)
IF keyword_set(YSUN) THEN YS=ysun ELSE YS=!YSUN
YS=float(YS)
IF keyword_set(ZSUN) THEN BEGIN
  IF (abs(zsun) GT 0.1) THEN print, 'Warning: do you really want the sun above 0.1 kpc?'
  ZS=zsun
ENDIF ELSE BEGIN
  ZS=!ZSUN
```

```

ENDELSE
ZS=float(ZS)
IF keyword_set(ROTXY) THEN rot=rotxy/180.*!pi ELSE rot=0.
deg=180!/pi & sr=1/deg
IF keyword_set(ABSMAG) THEN Mab=absmag ELSE Mab=0.
IF keyword_set(PITCH) THEN ptch=pitch ELSE ptch=13.0
IF keyword_set(RINNER) THEN rin=rinner ELSE rin=1.

;-----
; -----Parse input-----
;f1=float(f1) & g1=float(g1) & h1=float(h1)

from=strmid(itype,0,3) & to=strmid(itype,4,3) & mid=strmid(itype,3,1)
IF (mid NE '2') THEN stop, 'Input format for itype is XXX2YYYY'

; -----Choices for coordinate systems-----
; Note Could be extended for Mag Stream/Sgr stream coords
coord=['xyz','rlz','dlb','mlb','XYZ','RTZ','DTP','SAZ']
icoord=[ 0, 0, 0, 0, 1, 1, 1, 1]
type=['solar-centric', 'galacto-centric']

;-----Determine which type of system we're going from/to
i1=where(from EQ coord,NI1) & i2=where(to EQ coord,NI2)
IF (NI1 EQ 0 OR NI2 EQ 0) THEN BEGIN
  IF (NI1 EQ 0) THEN print, 'Input coordinates: ', from, ' is incorrect'
  IF (NI2 EQ 0) THEN print, 'Input coordinates: ', to, ' is incorrect'
  print, 'Coordinate choices are : ', coord
  stop
ENDIF
intype=type[icoord[i1]] & outtype=type[icoord[i2]]
print, 'Converting from '+from+'('+intype+')'+' to '+to+'('+outtype+')'

;=====
=====
; Convert input coordinates into cartesian coords
; either solar-centric (xyz) or Galacto-centric (XX,YY,ZZ)
; depending on input
;=====
=====
CASE 1 OF
(intype EQ 'solar-centric'): BEGIN
  CASE 1 OF
    ;-----
    (from EQ 'xyz'): BEGIN
      x=f1 & y=g1 & z=h1
    END
    ;-----

```

```

(from EQ 'rlz'): BEGIN
  r=f1 & l=g1 & z=h1
  x=r*cos(l*sr) & y=r*sin(l*sr)
END
;-----
(from EQ 'dlb'): BEGIN
  d=f1 & l=g1 & b=h1
  x=d*cos(b*sr)*cos(l*sr) & y=d*cos(b*sr)*sin(l*sr) & z=d*sin(b*sr)
END
;-----
(from EQ 'mlb'): BEGIN
  m=f1 & l=g1 & b=h1
  d=0.01*10^(0.2*(m-Mab))
  x=d*cos(l*sr)*cos(b*sr) & y=d*sin(l*sr)*cos(b*sr) & z=d*sin(b*sr)
END
;-----
ENDCASE
END
(intype EQ 'galacto-centric'): BEGIN
CASE 1 OF
;-----
  (from EQ 'XYZ'): BEGIN
    XX=f1 & YY=g1 & ZZ=h1
  END
;-----
  (from EQ 'RTZ'): BEGIN
    RR=f1 & TT=g1 & ZZ=h1
    XX=RR*cos(TT*sr) & YY=RR*sin(TT*sr)
  END
;-----
  (from EQ 'DTP'): BEGIN
    DD=f1 & TT=g1 & PP=h1
    XX=DD*cos(TT*sr)*cos(PP*sr) & YY=DD*sin(TT*sr)*cos(PP*sr) & ZZ=DD*sin(PP*sr)
  END
;-----
  (from EQ 'SAZ'): BEGIN
    RR=f1 & AA=g1 & ZZ=h1
    b=tan(ptch/180.*!pi)
    TT=(1.0/b)*alog(RR/rin)+AA ;was -AA
    XX=RR*cos(TT) & YY=RR*sin(TT)
  END
;-----
ENDCASE
END
ENDCASE
;=====
=====
;=====

```

=====

;

=====

; Convert the input cartesian coordinates into the output cartesian coordinates
; Rotate output cartesian coordinates if requested.

;

=====

CASE 1 OF

(intype EQ 'solar-centric' AND outtype EQ 'galacto-centric'): BEGIN
 XX=x+XS & YY=y+YS & ZZ=z+ZS
 IF keyword_set(ROTTY) THEN rotate_xy, XX, YY, rot, 0., 0., XX, YY
 END

(intype EQ 'galacto-centric' AND outtype EQ 'solar-centric'): BEGIN
 IF keyword_set(ROTTY) THEN rotate_xy, XX, YY, rot, 0., 0., XX, YY
 x=XX-XS & y=YY-YS & z=ZZ-ZS
 END

(intype EQ 'solar-centric' AND outtype EQ 'solar-centric'): BEGIN
 dum=0.0
 END

(intype EQ 'galacto-centric' AND outtype EQ 'galacto-centric'): BEGIN
 IF keyword_set(ROTTY) THEN rotate_xy, XX, YY, rot, 0., 0., XX, YY
 END

ENDCASE

;

=====

;

=====

;

=====

; Convert output cartesian coordinate into the
; correct coordinate system

;

=====

CASE 1 OF

(outtype EQ 'solar-centric'): BEGIN
 CASE 1 OF

 ;-----
 (to EQ 'xyz'): BEGIN
 f2=x & g2=y & h2=z
 END

 ;-----
 (to EQ 'rlz'): BEGIN
 f2=sqrt(x*x+y*y) & g2=atan(y,x)*deg & h2=z

```

END
;-----
(to EQ 'dlb'): BEGIN
f2=sqrt(x*x+y*y+z*z) & g2=atan(y,x)*deg & h2=asin(z/f2)*deg
END
;-----
(to EQ 'mlb'): BEGIN
f2=sqrt(x*x+y*y+z*z) & g2=atan(y,x)*deg & h2=asin(z/f2)*deg
f2=Mab+5*log10(f2)+10.
END
;-----
ENDCASE
END
(outtype EQ 'galacto-centric'): BEGIN
CASE 1 OF
;-----
(to EQ 'XYZ'): BEGIN
f2=XX & g2=YY & h2=ZZ
END
;-----
(to EQ 'RTZ'): BEGIN
f2=sqrt(XX*XX+YY*YY) & g2=atan(YY,XX)*deg & h2=ZZ
END
;-----
(to EQ 'DTP'): BEGIN
f2=sqrt(XX*XX+YY*YY+ZZ*ZZ) & g2=atan(YY,XX)*deg & h2=asin(ZZ/f2)*deg
END
(to EQ 'SAZ'): BEGIN
tpi=2*pi
b=tan(ptch/180.*pi)
th=- (1/b)*alog(sqrt(XX*XX+YY*YY)) +atan(YY,XX) + 100*tpi ; was -atan
wraps=fix( (th+0.00001)/tpi )
f2=sqrt(XX*XX+YY*YY)
g2=th-wraps*tpi
h2=ZZ
END
;-----
ENDCASE
END
ENDCASE
;=====
=====
;=====
=====

;=====
=====
; If using an azimuthal coordinate system on output (either theta or longitude)

```

```

; *check to see if the range should go from (-180 to 180) default or (0 360) if /AZ360 is set
; *check to see if output should be sorted by azimuth (to avoid crossovers)
;=====
=====
azcoord=['rlz','dlb','mlb','RTZ','DTP']
iaz=where(to EQ azcoord,NAZ)
IF (NAZ EQ 1) THEN BEGIN
  IF keyword_set(AZ360) THEN BEGIN
    ii=where(g2 LT 0,NII)
    IF (NII GT 0) THEN g2[ii]=g2[ii]+360.
  ENDIF
  IF keyword_set(AZSORT) THEN BEGIN
    is=sort(g2)
    f2=f2[is] & g2=g2[is] & h2=h2[is]
  ENDIF
ENDIF
;=====
=====

end

```

IDL Script That Helps the Former Code Execute by Christopher Beaumont

```

;+
; PURPOSE:
; This procedure converts galactic coordinates to
; equatorial (RA-Dec) coordinates.
;
; INPUTS:
; x : Array of galactic x coordinates, in parsecs
; y : Array of galactic y coordinates, in parsecs
; z : Array of galactic z coordinates, in parsecs
;
; OUTPUTS:
; ra : RA coordinates, in degrees
; dec : Dec coordinates, in degrees
;
; ASSUMPTIONS:
; The galactic coordinates of the sun are assumed to be
; (-8500, 0, 25) pc. To use different values, use these commands:
; defsysv, '!XSUN', new_xsun_value
;-
pro xyz2radec, x, y, z, ra, dec,d

;- define sun coordinates, if needed
defsysv, '!XSUN', exists=has_xsun

```

```
defsysv, '!YSUN', exists=has_ysun  
defsysv, '!ZSUN', exists=has_zsun
```

```
if has_xsun eq 0 then defsysv, '!XSUN', -8500  
if has_ysun eq 0 then defsysv, '!YSUN', 0  
if has_zsun eq 0 then defsysv, '!ZSUN', 25
```

```
;- galactic cartesian to galactic d, l, b  
mw_coord, x, y, z, 'XYZ2dlb', d, l, b
```

```
;- galactic d, l, b to ra dec  
euler, l, b, ra, dec, 2
```

```
end
```

```
;  
;+  
; This example program shows how to read in a file of  
; spiral arm locations (a catalog of x, y, z points),  
; convert them to RA/dec pairs, and write out to a new file  
;-  
pro test
```

```
infile = 'spiral_arms_galactocentric.csv'  
outfile = 'spiral_arms_equatorial.csv'
```

```
;- read file  
readcol, infile, x, y, z
```

```
;- conversion  
xyz2radec, x, y, z, ra, dec
```

```
;- write file  
writecol, outfile, ra, dec  
end
```

APPENDIX B

THIS APPENDIX CONTAINS DATA SPREAD-SHEETS FOR THE POINTS FOR EACH ARM AS PER THE MODEL DEVELOPED BY THE AUTHOR FOR THE PURPOSES OF THIS PAPER.

Please see the attached folder for the Excel Workbooks containing this data

APPENDIX C

THIS APPENDIX CONTAINS DATA CONTAINS VISUAL DATA (IMAGES) OF NESSIE-CANDIDATES THAT WERE FOUND USING THE WORLD-WIDE TELESCOPE UTILITY. A BRIEF DISCUSSION OF A CHALLENGE FACED DURING VISUAL INSPECTION IS FOUND IN FIG C2.

Fig C1 -- A filamentary object appears to be at the spine of the Norma arm

Fig C2 -- A periodic, filamentary IRDC seems nestled between various 'background' arms. it is not clear whether this is a single IRDC or numerous ones superimposed. This is a common hurdle during visual inspection.

Fig C3 -- A dark, filament seems to be nestled between the dots that signify the Scutum Centaurus Arm.

Fig C4 -- A filamentary cloud seems to sketch out the Perseus Arm.